

USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN ELEMENTARY GROUPS

Eshboltayeva Lola Baxtiyorovna

Termiz university of economics and service

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11501865>

Abstract

Authentic materials are one of common materials in teaching English. Most of teacher usually use them to be implemented into their classroom. One of the reasons of the teachers they use it in the classroom is in order to give the students example of the real use of English in social life. Other than authentic materials, the teachers also usually use textbook. It is because textbook gives much easier for the teachers to use it in the classroom and also for the students to studied at home. In implementing the authentic materials is not as easy as using textbook. The teachers need to be creative to select and modify the authentic materials to be able to be implemented. It is because the authentic materials are not produced for pedagogical purposes. So, in this study, the objectives of the researcher are to seek about the perception of using authentic materials in the classroom, the reasons of the teachers about the perception, and also the way of the teachers when implementing the authentic materials in the classroom. Regarding the objectives above, the qualitative research is appropriate to be conducted in this study. It is in order to get the deep data from the research subject. To get the data, this study uses interview and observation. By the interview, it gets the answer of all the research questions. And by the observation, it gets the supporting data from the interview.

Keywords: Teachers' perception, authentic materials, implementation.

INTRODUCTION

Authentic materials are common materials used by many teachers in their teaching language. There are many reasons why an English teacher using them. Some researchers also have found that authentic materials have many benefits in teaching language process. Peacock (1997) said that authentic materials have a positive effect on students' motivation in learning foreign language. It is also quoted by Berardo (2006) from Widdowson that the language presented in the classroom should be authentic. Authentic materials are common materials used by many teachers in their teaching language. There are many reasons why an English teacher using them. Some researchers also have found that authentic materials have many benefits in teaching language process. Peacock (1997) said that authentic materials have a positive effect on students' motivation in learning foreign language. It is also quoted by Berardo (2006) from Widdowson that the language presented in the classroom should be authentic materials. Like what has done by Mamo (2013), Rasheed (2014), Belaid (2015), Akbari and Razavi (2016), and Ahmed (2017), mostly they talked about the use of authentic materials. Mamo (2013) did a research on the use of authentic materials in teaching listening skills to college students. He found that such authentic materials on listening like song, etc. expose the students to the real world. Such teachers also awares to use authentic materials in listening skill. He suggested that students level, interest, relevance and quality of the materials should be appropriate to the authentic materials. It means that between authentic materials and the students need should be relevance (Mamo, 2013). In addition to Mamo, the closely finding found by Akbari and Razavi (2016), they found that authentic materials are exposing the students to the real language and real society. They also found that most of the teachers

believed that the language level of the text and the course objectives are the guiding criteria for selecting appropriate text. Other studies on authentic materials are also done by Rasheed (2014), Belaidi (2015) and Ahmed (2017). Rasheed (2014) found that the teachers believed that authentic materials could help the students practice English in real life. He also found that the students were motivated in learning English by using authentic materials. Moreover, Belaidi (2015) held a research on teacher's attitudes and perceptions on using authentic materials. He found that some EFL teachers emphasized on their regular use of authentic materials in their language classes. Most of teachers also hold positive attitude in using authentic materials. Meanwhile, Ahmed (2017) mentioned that some authentic materials used in classroom are divided into four parts. They are audio visual, paper, realia, and audio. Materials that include to the audio visual are like movies, cartoon, serial dramas, sport, and interview. While the materials that include to the paper such as pictures, posters, photograph, calendar, cue cards, newspaper, magazines, etc. Materials that include to the realia are restaurant menu, brochure, air ticket, wedding card, etc. While that include to the audio are news radio, interview, commentary, etc. (Ahmed, 2017). In addition of those researchers, about the problems of the teachers in using authentic materials, Anam (2012) stated that the difficulties in authentic materials are a lot. For the example, the teachers have to prepare the authentic material as good as possible, they also have to filter the authentic materials so they are appropriate for learning process. Because the teachers have to prepare and filter the authentic materials as good as possible, the teachers need much time to do that. other materials (Anam: 2012). From those findings of the studies, there is limited information about teachers' perceptions and the ways on using authentic materials. Hence, it is very interesting to know teachers' perceptions about using authentic materials, the reasons for holding such perspective, and the ways they have in using authentic materials. Rasheed (2014) in his research believed that authentic materials could help the students practice English in real life and the students were motivated in learning English. in addition, Belaidi (2015) found that some EFL teachers, emphasized on their regular use of authentic materials in their language classes. Most of teachers also hold positive attitude in using authentic materials. There are some advantages in using authentic materials for language teaching. Richard (2001) quoted from Philips, Shettlesworth, Clarke and Peacock stated that authentic materials have good effects to motivate the students. First, authentic materials give authentic cultural information about the target language. Second, they also provide exposure to real language and relate more closely to students' needs. The last, they can support a more creative approach to teaching. Tamo (2009) stated, "Authentic materials have a positive effect on learner motivation." Moreover, there are several advantages in using authentic materials for teaching English. They are exposing to real discourse for the learner, informing the learner what is happening in the real world, producing a sense of achievement, able to be used under different circumstances, ideal to teach/practice skimming and scanning for reading texts, containing a wide variety of text types, able to encourage reading for pleasure because they contain interesting topics to the learners (Martinez, 2012). From those ideas, it can be concluded that most of them agree that authentic materials are very useful in motivating students' learning. They also agree that authentic materials can stimulate students to study more about the language on their own way when the teacher have introduced the authentic materials during the teaching process. However, there are also many disadvantages in using

authentic materials for teaching English. Richard (2001) stated that authentic materials often contain difficult language and unneeded vocabulary items. They are also a burden for the teachers. own way when the teacher have introduced the authentic materials during the teaching process. Using authentic materials is one of the big problems that many experts on language teaching have tried to implement it. In order to the advantages and the positive effect of authentic materials in developing student's skill on language, to implement the authentic materials is not as easy as using the coursebook. (Kilickaya, 2004) It is because there are also some problems that have found by some researchers when the teacher using them. The disadvantages normally appear because the authenticity of the language itself. Therefore, they will disappear if the teachers anticipate the problems. They will also be reduced to the students' interest of language using. Tamo (2009) quoted from Chaves stated that the students still enjoy the language since they can interact with the real language in use. It seems that the learners need pedagogical support when learning with authentic materials. Anam (2012) stated that the difficulties in using authentic materials are a lot. The difficulties or the problems appeared not only during teaching process, but they also appeared when they were preparing the authentic materials, during the process of teaching, and the way.

METHOD

This research is conducted by using a qualitative method. Specifically, it uses a descriptive qualitative research method. According to Nassaji (2015) descriptive qualitative research method is commonly used in researching language. He said that this method has been very common procedures for conducting research in many disciplines, including education, psychology, language, and social sciences. In that way, it is very good to conduct this research by qualitative method. The characteristic of qualitative research method is naturalness of the data. It works with a wide range of data including recorded interview, various types of text, and images. (Dornyei, 2007) According to the objective of the study, this research needs to be as natural as possible to get the validity of the result of the study. This study also needs to be variety so the result can be reach. In that way, qualitative research method is very needed. In this case, the teachers that were researched were the teachers in an Islamic Senior High School in Surabaya. In other word, the researcher in this study was done by myself. There were two teachers that became the subject in this study. The first teacher has already been teaching English there for about 8 years. The second teacher is still new teacher there. She has been teaching there for about 2 years.

CONCLUSION

The authentic materials are very important to be implemented in the classroom as teaching materials. It is in order to make the students get motivated and interested to study English more and more. The authentic materials are very easy to get so the teachers should not be aware for the availability of them. They just need the internet and find the authentic materials they like from the internet. In implementing the authentic materials, the teacher should prepare everything well before they come to the class. it is in order to get successful during the teaching process in the class. The teachers have to be more creative in choosing and selecting the authentic materials for the students. So, the students really get interest and motivated by the authentic materials.

References:

1. Abbas Pourhosein Gilakjani, Narjes Banou Sabouri. (2017). Teachers' Beliefs in English Language Teaching and Learning: A Review of the Literature. Canadian Center of Science and Education, 78-86.
2. Ahmed, S. (2017). Authentic ELT Materials in the Language Classroom: An Overview. Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Research, 181-202.
3. Amirin, D. T. (1986). Menyusun Rencana Penelitian. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
4. Anam, K. (2012). Teachers' Difficulties in Using Authentic Materials For Teaching English in English Education Departement of Tarbiyah Faculty of IAIN Sunan Ampel, Surabaya. UIN Sunan Ampel.
5. Anjaniputra, A. G. (2013). Teacher's Strategies in Teaching Speaking to Students. Journal of English and Education, 1-8.
6. Ardila, F. (2015). An Analysis of Teachers' Perception on The Use of Authentic Reading Materials. PendidikanBahasa Inggris STKIP PGRI Sumatera Barat.
7. Arikunto, S. (2002). "Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktek" . Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY